

A SURVEY ON THE MATHEMATICS ANXIETY OF STUDENTS: A CONVERGENT STUDY

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 29

Issue 1

Pages: 51-72

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2740

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14524254

Manuscript Accepted: 11-19-2024

A Survey on the Mathematics Anxiety of Students: A Convergent Study

Alvin D. Libre,* Jubert E. Gulo

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study aimed to describe the lived experiences of first-year students in a local college regarding their anxiety about learning mathematics. This study engaged a mixed-method design, utilizing a parallel convergent approach. The participants of the study were the first-year students across all programs. There were 258 students who were randomly selected for quantitative and 14 for the qualitative, 14 for in-depth interview which were purposively selected. Based on the results of the study, it was determined that the level of mathematics anxiety is high. The results from the quantitative and qualitative converged when they were being corroborated. The results confirm the Cognitive Appraisal Theory, which posits that individuals' interpretations of events significantly influence their emotional responses. This suggests that helping students reframe their perceptions of mathematical tasks and challenges, as well as providing supportive learning environments, may help alleviate students' mathematics anxiety and improve their understanding and performance in the course subject.

Keywords: *mathematics anxiety, mixed methods, first-year students, Philippines*

Introduction

Mathematics anxiety is a pervasive issue among students, impacting their performance across various academic subjects, with mathematics being particularly affected. This challenge is noteworthy considering the indispensable role of mathematics in modern society, where quantitative skills are fundamental for success in diverse fields, as outlined in the Mathematics in the Modern World course. Students with inadequate mathematical abilities often encounter difficulties in academic and professional environments, exacerbating their anxiety and hindering their progress. Consequently, addressing math anxiety becomes essential not only for individual academic achievement but also for cultivating a competent workforce capable of navigating the complexities of contemporary challenges, as emphasized in the Mathematics in the Modern World course (Luttenberger, 2018).

In Indonesia, mathematics anxiety is a factor affecting students' academic performance. Data were collected through observations, interviews, and questionnaires on mathematics anxiety. Based on the result, the percentage of mathematics anxiety was 29.4% at the high, 41.2% in the middle, and 29.4% at the low levels. This may occur because students consider mathematics a difficult subject, perceive exams as intimidating, and often feel dizzy when dealing with math exams. Although students appreciate teachers' classroom teaching styles that make them comfortable, their experience differs during math tests. Students also experience anxiety, nervousness, and fear when unprepared for a math test (Anugrah et al., 2019). In the Philippines, mathematics anxiety becomes evident that a substantial proportion of participants, specifically 233 individuals, demonstrated a considerably high extent of anxiety towards mathematics, translating to 60.5% of the total sample of students. On the other hand, 145 students, constituting 37.7% of the participants, exhibited a milder manifestation of anxiety in relation to mathematics. Remarkably, only seven students, equivalent to 1.8% of the sample, displayed a moderate level of anxiety. This distribution offers insights into the prevailing degrees of mathematics anxiety within the study population, emphasizing the prominence of high anxiety level and signaling the need for a closer examination of potential influencing factors (Rahaman et al., 2023).

This study holds profound significance across various levels. It carries the potential to empower students individually by alleviating mathematics anxiety, thereby fostering a positive self-perception and enhancing their overall mental health. At an educational level, it stands to guide educators and institutions in developing more effective teaching methods and curriculum frameworks that actively address anxiety and improve learning outcomes. Moreover, on a societal scale, it can contribute to economic prosperity, promote equitable access to education, and address the increasing prevalence of mental health challenges among students. The urgency of this research is underscored by the paramount need to prioritize students' emotional well-being, adapt to evolving educational needs, and ensure a sustainable future societies.

In this context, relevant international studies have explored mathematics anxiety in students, primarily focusing on experiences of anxiety. Singh (2022) utilized a concurrent mixed methods approach and triangulation design to investigate the research problem. Participants were grade eleven students and secondary mathematics teachers from four private schools in an eastern state in India. Delgado & Kassim (2019) conducted a quantitative study exploring the mathematics anxiety of five hundred sixteen junior high school students with ages ranging from eleven to seventeen. Luu-Thi et al. (2021) examined 1,548 high school students (570 males and 978 females) from high schools in Vietnam, using the Revised Version of the Mathematics Anxiety Rating Scale. They employed a multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) test, Pearson correlation, and multiple linear regression to analyze the data, focusing on students' anxiety in math. However, none of these studies investigated the mathematics anxiety of first-year students in the Mathematics in the Modern World course.

This work will be shared with educational institutions and relevant organizations, serving as a foundation for academic discussions and

conferences related to the study's topic. There are also plans to publish this paper on educational websites and present it at various conferences. Additionally, the result of the study will be dissemination at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology (KCAST), where it can be displayed for other researchers to study and explore. The goal is to ensure a well-planned distribution strategy to reach a wider audience and maximize the impact of the research.

Research Questions

This study investigated mathematics anxiety among first-year college students, using a mixed methods research approach. The purpose of employing this approach was to gather both quantitative and qualitative data concurrently, merge the findings, and utilize them to address the research problem at hand. This research design allowed for the strengths of each data collection method to offset the limitations of the other, resulting in a more comprehensive understanding of the research problem through the combined analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data.

1. What is the perceived level of mathematics anxiety among first-year college students?
2. What are the experiences of first-year college students in learning mathematics?
3. To what degree do the quantitative data corroborate with the qualitative data?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a mixed methods design, which involves the interlinking of qualitative and quantitative components to provide a more comprehensive account of the research problem. According to Halcomb and Hickman (2015), this integration is crucial for the rigor of mixed methods research, and it can occur at any stage(s) of the research process. The term "mixing" refers to the process of linking the qualitative and quantitative elements to produce a fuller account of the research problem.

According to Bryman (2007), mixed methods research plays a vital role in research beyond mere validation. It enables the integration of multiple research methods, leading to a comprehensive and holistic perspective on the subject of study. This approach not only validates the research but also allows for a more profound understanding of the phenomenon under investigation. By combining the results obtained from different methods, researchers can potentially reveal new insights that might have been overlooked using a single-method approach.

The research design selected for this study was a convergent parallel mixed method. In this design, both types of data are collected concurrently and given equal priority. The survey was collected first, followed by focus group or one-on-one interviews. The two sets of data are analyzed separately, and the results are then merged, with the combined results being interpreted. This design is appropriate for the study as it aims to explore the convergence, divergence, contradictions, or relationships between the two sources of data (Hanson et al., 2005).

The convergent parallel design, also known as the convergent/triangulation design, involves the simultaneous implementation of both quantitative and qualitative studies during the same phase of the research process. In this design, both methods have equal priority, enabling them to play an equally important role in addressing the research problem. This design maintains the independence of the studies during data collection and analysis and then merges or combines the results during the overall interpretation (Petrosyan, 2018).

To gain a comprehensive understanding of the topic, this study was conducted using the convergent parallel design, which is a mixed-method design. The research process can be represented by two components: qualitative and quantitative (Morse, 1991). In a convergent parallel design, the researcher simultaneously conducts the quantitative and qualitative elements in the same phase of the research process, weighing the methods equally, analyzing the two components independently, and interpreting the results together. The researcher aims to triangulate the methods for corroboration and validation by directly comparing the quantitative statistical results and qualitative findings. In the research process, two datasets were obtained, analyzed separately, and compared (Demir & Pismek, 2018).

Under a convergent parallel design, data from qualitative sources such as face-to-face interviews, online interviews, audio recordings, and transcriptions, were collected alongside quantitative data obtained from a survey questionnaire. These data will be analyzed simultaneously to uncover patterns and insights. For the qualitative phase, a discourse and thematic analysis will be used in order to analyze the experiences of the first-year college students regarding their mathematics anxiety in their learning of Mathematics in the Modern World course. For the quantitative data, statistical analysis will be employed to get the results on the profiling, experiences of the first-year college student, significant differences in the status, and extent of how quantitative data corroborate qualitative data.

Consequently, this research employed a descriptive-comparative approach, which involved comparing and contrasting the collected results to draw meaningful conclusions. By utilizing both quantitative and qualitative research methods, this study aimed to enhance our understanding of the mathematics anxiety effect among first-year students and provide a foundation and intervention for effective teaching strategies and techniques. Hence, the study contains both quantitative and qualitative research methods (Richardson, 2018).

In addition, phenomenological inquiry were utilized in this study to further develop the qualitative frame. This methodology assisted the discovery and understanding within the rich environment evolving within the experiences of the participants. A phenomenology

focuses on the commonality of a lived experience within a particular group. Typically, interviews will be conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data such as documents and observations may also be used (Creswell, 2013). On the other hand, the qualitative phase of this study utilized a phenomenological approach, which reflects an epistemological perspective that acknowledges the validity of multiple subjective truths. Qualitative data collection methods such as focus group discussions or one-on-one interviews will be also employed effectively to glean insights into the social norms of the community, saturate the data obtained from in-depth interviews, and establish themes based on the researcher's collected data (Groenewald, 2004).

Participants

Quantitative Phase

The respondents of this study were first-year college students across all programs in Kapalong College Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology during the first semester of school year 2023-2024. They were chosen as the respondents because the study is about the mathematics anxiety of first-year students in a Local College. Since the study purports to involve students who are first-year students in a local college, it would be fitting and valid to include first-year college students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology.

Further, the respondents were determined through sampling method, specifically, stratified random sampling to establish randomness and maintain scientific rigor in the study. This method involves dividing the population into smaller groups, or "strata," and randomly selecting a sample from each stratum. The per-stratum samples are then combined to create an overall stratified random sample. An alternative to simple random sampling, stratified random sampling ensures that each stratum is represented in the sample and can provide more accurate results when analyzing subgroups within the population (Nguyen et al., 2020).

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

<i>Course/Program</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Bachelor of Elementary Education (Generalist)	187	14	0.41%
Bachelor of Public Administration	440	33	0.96%
Bachelor of Science in Agriculture (Animal Science)	134	10	0.29%
Bachelor of Science in Agriculture (Horticulture)	231	17	0.50%
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (Financial Management)	317	24	0.69%
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (Human Resource Management)	121	9	0.26%
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration(Marketing Management)	396	30	0.86%
Bachelor of Science in Criminology	692	52	1.51%
Bachelor of Science in Office Administration	393	29	0.85%
Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English	223	17	0.49%
Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Filipino	191	14	0.42%
Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Mathematics	119	9	0.26%
Total	3,444	258	7.49%

This sampling method was particularly appropriate in this study because the respondents, who are first-year college students were randomly selected based on strata, which in this case are from all course programs in Kapalong College Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. This also ensures that all of the respondents in the population have equal chances of being selected. The researcher wrote a formal request letter to the College Registrar and gained access to the population of first-year college students across all programs. The researcher then gathered the data from the population of mathematics education students to compute the sample. After getting the data, the researcher sent the information to her statistician for the computation of the study sample.

The study was conducted among first-year students enrolled across all programs. The institution has a total of 3444 first-year students, consisting of 187 Bachelor of Elementary Education (Generalist) students, 440 Bachelor of Public Administration students, 134 Bachelor of Science in Agriculture (Animal Science) students, 231 Bachelor of Science in Agriculture (Horticulture) students, 317 Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (Financial Management) students, 121 Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (Human Resource Management) students, 396 Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (Marketing Management) students, 692 Bachelor of Science in Criminology students, 393 Bachelor of Science in Office Administration students, 223 Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English students, 191 Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Filipino students, and 119 Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Mathematics students.

However, the sample appropriate for the study was computed by the statistician, which included 258 out of 3,444 first-year students, 14 out of 187 Bachelor of Elementary Education (Generalist) students, 33 out of 440 Bachelor of Public Administration students, 10 out of 134 Bachelor of Science in Agriculture (Animal Science) students, 17 out of 231 Bachelor of Science in Agriculture (Horticulture) students, 24 out of 317 Bachelor of Science in Business Administration(Financial Management) students, 9 out of 121 Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (Human Resource Management) students, 30 out of 396 Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (Marketing Management) students, 52 out of 692 Bachelor of Science in Criminology students, 29 out of 393

Bachelor of Science in Office Administration students, 17 out of 223 Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English students, 14 out of 191 Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Filipino students, and 9 out of 119 Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Mathematics students. In total, 258 students were sampled out of the 3,444 first-year students enrolled across all programs.

Qualitative Phase

In contrast, subject selection in qualitative research was purposeful. In this phase, non-probability sampling specifically purposive sampling technique was utilized. Participants were selected who could best inform the research questions and enhance their understanding of the phenomenon under study (Kuper et al., 2008). Only 14 participants among the first-year college students were enjoined in the qualitative phase: fourteen (14) for in-depth interview. Hence, no focus group discussion's conducted. All of them were enrolled across all programs at KCAST and he or she is a first-year student. It should be noted that participants in the qualitative phase must not have participated in the data collection of the quantitative phase.

Table 2. Profile of the Participants

<i>Assigned Code</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Course/Program</i>
IDI-01	Female	Bachelor of Public Administration
IDI-02	Male	Bachelor of Science in Office Administration
IDI-03	Female	Bachelor of Science in Criminology
IDI-04	Male	Bachelor of Science in Agriculture(Horticulture)
IDI-05	Female	Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English
IDI-06	Female	Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (Marketing Management)
IDI-07	Male	Bachelor of Science in Agriculture(Animal Science)
IDI-08	Male	Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (Financial Management)
IDI-09	Female	Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Filipino
IDI-10	Female	Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (Human Resource Management)
IDI-11	Male	Bachelor of Elementary Education(Generalist)
IDI-12	Male	Bachelor of Public Administration
IDI-13	Female	Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Mathematics
IDI-14	Female	Bachelor of Science in Agriculture(Horticulture)

Instrument

Quantitative Phase

The researcher utilized an adapted survey questionnaire for mathematics anxiety which was adapted from Taguinod (2022). The said questionnaire used a five- point Likert Scale which had the following indicators: the following indicators: physical and emotional factors, assessment factor, and social factor.

In a ve-point Likert Scale, participants were only required to rate and tick one box among one (lowest) to five (highest) in each question. Moreover, the Likert Scale was good for measuring constructs, attitudes, and stimuli that are not readily perceivable by human senses. Despite the questionnaire being adapted, it was still subjected to expert validation.

Qualitative Phase

As to the qualitative phase, a set of researcher-made grand tour questions were devised by the researcher and validated by the panel of experts. This was a set of open-ended questions that was developed based on the results of the survey. This was used as a compass for the in-depth interviews. Of all the participants who answered the survey questionnaire in the previous phase, fourteen were purposively selected to undergo the IDI. Interviews were suitable for gleaning insights, stories, experiences, opinions, and other useful information which could not be expressed with the use of numbers.

Procedure

There were several steps in the data collection process. The following procedures were followed during the conduct of the study:

Quantitative Phase

In the quantitative phase, an adapted questionnaire was used for the mathematics anxiety of first-year college students. It was administered to a group of first-year students who were in a face-to-face learning set-up. In addition, the researcher wrote a letter of request to the school administrator, asking an approval to conduct the study to their respective school and students. The results were tallied, computed, and analyzed to corroborate the results of the qualitative data. The qualitative and quantitative phases of the study were done simultaneously.

Qualitative Phase

For the qualitative phase, a one-on-one interview was conducted to the identified participants in order to gather the lived experiences

of these first-year students with regards to their mathematics anxiety in their learning on Mathematics in the Modern World course. An interview guide was used both for the in-depth interview and focus group discussion. Hence, to ensure authenticity of selection, the researcher invited through personal contact the informants and they were informed of the tasks and that includes the time set for everyone's convenience (Creswell, 2013).

The focus group discussion centered on the exploration of individuals' opinions, experiences, concerns, and desires regarding the specific issues at hand. According to Traynor (2015), this method typically involves bringing together a group of individuals who share a common characteristic, facilitated by a researcher, to engage in group interactions, exchange perspectives on a specific topic, discuss personal experiences, and provide suggestions. It's important to note that the methodology of focus group research explicitly emphasizes the use of interaction. The discussions took various forms, including one-on-one sessions, and it was recorded through audio recording, with additional notes taken.

For the qualitative data collection, focus group discussions and in-depth interviews were conducted to gather the lived experiences of the participants with regard to mathematics anxiety. To ensure the authenticity of the selection, I invited, through personal contact, the informants, and they were informed of the tasks to be done (Boyce & Neale, 2006), as well as the venue and the time set for everyone's convenience (Creswell, 2013). In the conduct of the in-depth interview, I used the prepared to facilitate a set of questions, and I gave follow-up questions to ensure saturation of answers. During the conduct of the interview, I thoroughly discussed the ethical considerations with the participants.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Phase

In the quantitative data analysis, descriptive statistics such as the mean were utilized to assess the average responses of the respondents. The survey data, which was collected, served as the basis for in-depth analysis. Upon retrieval of the questionnaires, the data was tallied and treated accordingly. The survey data was further analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for both descriptive and inferential statistics. These statistical treatments were applied to ascertain the status of first-year college students.

Qualitative Phase

Regarding the qualitative data analysis, the researcher employed coding and thematic analysis. This involved examining the patterns and themes that emerged from the utterances or statements of the participants/informants during the one-on-one and focus group interviews. The themes were formulated with the purpose of analyzing the lived experiences of first-year college students in mathematics anxiety with their learning in Mathematics in the Modern World course. The data was carefully analyzed to identify and extract relevant themes that shed light on the research objectives and provide insights into the participants' experiences in this context.

Ethical Considerations

In order to uphold the trust of the first-year students from KCAST, the study prioritized their safety, anonymity, complete protection, and confidentiality as key concerns. Measures were taken to ensure that these ethical considerations were carefully addressed, aiming to maintain the trust of the participants throughout the course of the study.

The researcher diligently adhered to ethical principles including respect for persons, beneficence, justice, obtaining informed consent, and maintaining confidentiality to ensure that ethical standards were met. These principles guided the conduct of the study in a responsible and respectful manner, prioritizing the rights and well-being of the participants (Mack et al., 2005).

Respect for persons is an ethical principle that underscores the importance of treating research participants with courtesy and respect and acknowledging their autonomy in decision-making regarding their participation in a study (Munhall, 2012 & Scott, 2013). This principle necessitates providing participants with comprehensive information about the study and ensuring that they have a clear understanding of the research and any potential risks or benefits. Obtaining informed consent is a crucial aspect of adhering to this principle, as it signifies voluntary agreement based on an informed understanding. By upholding the principle of respect for persons, the researcher can ensure that the study is conducted ethically and in a manner that honors the rights and autonomy of the participants.

Before conducting the interviews, the researcher obtained permission from the participants and arranged the schedule in advance to avoid conflicts with their classes or other obligations. This was done to ensure that the researcher's presence would not disrupt the participants' schedules and to avoid the need for rescheduling or canceling the interviews.

During the conduct of my study, I established a respectful and courteous relationship with the participants and obtained their permission before recording the conversations. I also allowed the participants to ask questions at any time and maintained the confidentiality of the in-depth interviews and focused group discussion. In addition, the participants had the right to refuse to answer sensitive questions. By establishing rapport and acting with courtesy towards the participants, I was able to conduct the study in an ethical and respectful manner.

Consent is a fundamental aspect of research ethics and serves as a way to show respect to research participants. By obtaining informed consent, the participants are made fully aware of the objectives and purpose of the research they are being asked to participate in.

Written consent was obtained from the participants, certifying their approval to take part in the in-depth interviews and focused group discussions. They were provided with information about the results and findings of the study, ensuring transparency and keeping them informed (Creswell, 2012).

To ensure the ethical conduct of the study, I provided the participants with letters of permission and consent that outlined the details of the study, including the methods, design, and procedures. These letters were intended to help the participants understand the nature of the study and make informed decisions about whether to participate. Participants who decided not to participate were allowed to leave without any explanations and were assured that their data would remain confidential. The researcher also informed the participants that they had the right to be informed of the result of the study. By following these ethical guidelines, the researcher was able to ensure that the study was conducted responsibly and respectfully.

Beneficence, as an ethical principle, emphasizes the commitment to minimize risks and maximize the well-being of research participants. In this study, efforts were made to ensure the safety and protection of the participants. The anonymity of interviewees was maintained to prevent any potential risks to their privacy and confidentiality. All files of information were properly secured and not left unattended or unprotected (Bricki & Green, 2007).

To adhere to the principle of beneficence, I took steps to protect the anonymity and confidentiality of the participant's responses and personal identities. To minimize any potential risks, I did not engage in any face-to-face interactions with the participants and instead used a social media platform to communicate with them. By taking these measures, I was able to ensure the well-being and interests of the participants and demonstrate a commitment to ethical research practices.

Furthermore, the data collected from this research study was used only for the purposes outlined in the study. However, the results of the study may also be shared or disseminated through channels such as presentation to the institution, publication in scientific forums or journals, or presentation at conferences, either locally, nationally, or internationally. By disseminating the results of the study, the researcher aims to share the findings and contribute to the broader knowledge base in their field of study.

Confidentiality towards the data, results, and findings including the safeguard of participants, different techniques were used. Meaning, that all personal identities of the participants were hidden and not shown. All materials including audio records, encoded transcripts, notes, soft and hard copies of data and others should be eliminated right after the data is analyzed (Maree & Westhuizen, 2007).

To protect the participants' identity and ensure compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, I were used discrete coding to denote each participant's responses. This measure involved carefully phrasing any information that could potentially identify the participants in terms of their name, gender, ethnicity, or employment/location to avoid violating their anonymity. By using proper coding and other measures, I was able to protect the participants' identity and ensure that their privacy were respected.

Justice played a crucial role in this study, particularly in relation to first-year students experiencing mathematics anxiety. The researchers upheld ethical standards by respecting participants' rights, given the study's focus on first-year students. To promote fairness and equal opportunity, the researchers employed both random and purposive sampling techniques. Participation was entirely voluntary, with students free to decline without consequence. The study recognized participants' contributions through tokens of appreciation and proper acknowledgment, emphasizing their role in the research's success.

Furthermore, the principle of justice extended to the data collection and analysis processes. The researchers ensured justice by including only relevant participant utterances that aligned with the research objectives. These utterances were accurately transcribed, as emphasized by Munhall (2012) and Scott (2013), to maintain the integrity of the participants' voices and experiences. This approach not only respected the participants' input but also contributed to the overall validity and reliability of the study's findings in the context of mathematics anxiety among first-year students.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of data in both quantitative and qualitative phases. The first phase deals with the quantitative part which it displays the status of first-year students' mathematics anxiety and its variables that significantly predict mathematics anxiety. The second phase deals with the qualitative part which was presented in a matrix form. The matrix shows the responses of the participants on their lived experiences regarding their mathematics in learning. Also, the matrix contains the issues probed, core ideas, codes or categories, essential themes and the supporting theoretical perspectives. Further, another matrix shows the data integration of the salient quantitative and qualitative findings.

Status of Mathematics Anxiety

Mathematics Anxiety. Shown in Table 3 is the status of the mathematics anxiety of first-year students in Kapalong Agriculture of Sciences and Technology. It obtained an overall mean score of 3.53 with a description of High. This means that first-year students manifested oftentimes their mathematics anxiety. The variable of the study is mathematics anxiety which has three indicators namely: physical and emotional factors, assessment factors, and emotional factors

Physical and Emotional Factors. In terms of physical and emotional factors, the category mean is 3.50, which is described as high. This

means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Among the items under this indicator, encountering difficulties in maintaining regular sleep patterns following the completion of math assignments or on nights preceding math-related events got the highest mean of 3.61 which is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. On the other hand, the lowest item rated by the participants was experiencing an increased need to urinate during math classes, assignments, or assessments with a mean of 3.38. This rating is described as moderate. This means that it is sometimes manifested by the students.

Table 3. *Status of Mathematics Anxiety*

<i>Variables and Indicators</i>	<i>Mean Description</i>	
A. Physical and Emotional Factors		
1. Experiencing emotional distress, including anger, crying, and extreme frustration, when confronted with math tasks	3.52	High
2. Encountering a difficulties in maintaining regular sleep patterns following the completion of math assignments or on nights preceding math-related events.	3.61	High
3. Suffering from a headaches or neck stiffness when involved in mathematical thinking or activities.	3.53	High
4. Experiencing of an increased need to urinate during math classes, assignments, or assessments.	3.38	Moderate
5. Feeling of an accelerated heart rate during the execution of math-related tasks or contemplation of mathematical problems.	3.47	High
Category Mean	3.50	High
B. Assessment Factors		
1. Performing consistently below expectations on math tests compared to other subjects.	3.64	High
2. Feeling of need for more extensive preparation when studying for math tests than for tests in other subjects.	3.74	High
3. Encountering difficulty of maintaining focus during math tests, characterized by racing thoughts and moments of mental blankness.	3.68	High
4. having a lack of confidence in my abilities during math tests, regardless of the thoroughness of my preparation	3.73	High
5. Displaying an anxious behaviors such as fidgeting, pacing, making excuses, or avoiding specific situations while preparing for math tests.	3.41	Moderate
Category Mean	3.64	High
C. Social Factors		
1. Perceiving others to have a more mathematical or logical mind than I do.	3.61	High
2. Experiencing punishment or embarrassment in math class for not understanding something.	3.15	Moderate
3. Finding myself worried about other people's math abilities and comparing them to my own.	3.53	High
4. Relying on others to assist me with day-to-day math situations such as calculating tips and solving math problems.	3.45	Moderate
5. Feeling like I have never truly understood math and that I am merely faking my way through it.	3.45	Moderate
Category Mean	3.44	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.53	High

Assessment Factor. The assessment factor got a category mean of 3.64, which is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. The item feeling of need for more extensive preparation when studying for math tests than for tests in other subjects got the highest mean of 3.74, which is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Meanwhile, displaying of anxious behaviors such as fidgeting, pacing, making excuses, or avoiding specific situations while preparing for math tests is the lowest rated item which has a average category mean of 3.41. This means that it is sometimes manifested by the students.

Social Factor. In terms of social factor, the category mean is 3.44, which is described as average. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. The highest-rated item is perceiving others to have a more mathematical or logical mind than I do which has a category mean of 3.61 and is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. While experiencing a punishment or embarrassment in math class for not understanding something got the lowest category mean of 3.15 and is described as moderate. This means that it is sometimes manifested by students.

The Lived Experiences of First Year Students with Regards to their Mathematics Anxiety in Learning Mathematics

There are six essential themes which are created based from the in-depth interviews of the participants on the first research question. Before the presentation of the results from the interviews and discussions, profiles of the participants for the qualitative data collection are presented in table 4. The table represents the participants' profiles for the qualitative phases are selected purposively following the inclusion criteria: he or she must be a first year student enrolled across all program in KCAST. Based on the table, the profiles are divided into participants' sex and program. Further, Table 4 deals on the lived experiences of the first-year students mathematics anxiety in learning Mathematics. The essential themes which emerged from the transcriptions of the participants' responses for the research question number one are consisted of overarching themes which are summarized in the said table.

Table 4. *The Lived Experiences of First Year Students with Regards to their Anxiety in Learning Mathematics*

<i>Issues Probed</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Code / Categories</i>	<i>Essential Themes</i>	<i>Theoretical Support</i>
Difficulties in understanding and comprehending mathematical concepts Emotional and Psychological barriers in learning mathematics	Feeling confused during the learning process.	Difficulty understanding concepts	Encountering Cognitive Challenges	Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller, 1988)
	Difficulty remembering previously discussed concepts, methods, and formulas.			
	Difficulty in finding solutions or approaches to math problems.			
	Struggling to understand complex lessons due to perceived limitations in cognitive ability.	Personal Struggles with Problem-solving	Lack of understanding	
	Perceiving mathematics as difficult, especially when answering questions on the board.			
	Feeling pressured and overthinking of making small mistakes.			
	Struggling to understand explanations and find solutions through problem-solving.			
	Feeling unprepared, embarrassed, and disappointed for not being able to answer questions.			
	Taking longer to solve problems, feeling fatigued, and not finding the exact solution.			
	Struggling to grasp tricky mathematical concepts leads to confusion and feeling overwhelmed during learning.	Having Mathematical Anxiety	Experiencing Emotional and Psychological Crises	Self-Determination Theory (SDT) (Ryan & Deci, 2000)
	Difficulty understanding explanations and solving problems due to inadequate guidance, resulting in challenges when learning math.			
	Experiencing hardship in coping with challenging lessons and feeling intellectually limited in understanding mathematics easily.			
	Encountering challenging aspects of mathematics that require focused attention and effort to comprehend, despite the perceived difficulty.	Fear of Making Mistakes and Being Judged		
	Feeling disinterested and anxious with mathematics.			
	Feeling pressured with numerical nature of mathematics leading to confusion and loss of focus.			
Experiencing anxiety during quizzes and struggling to focus on studying mathematics due to distractions.	Building Positive Attitude from Negative Emotions			
Feeling anxious during oral presentations or board work stemming from a fear of being unable to answer.				
Struggling to understand key concepts and having fear of being judged when committing mistakes.				
Feeling anxious during oral presentations and class discussions of the teacher.	Feeling Stress During Discussion			
Feeling unprepared, embarrassed, and disappointed with oneself for not being able to answer questions.				
Doubting one's abilities but gradually gaining confidence through effort.				
Feeling uncomfortable from pedagogical approaches of the teacher.	Being Disinterested with Math Class	Lack of Motivation and Interest	Expectancy- Value Theory (Wigfield & Eccles, 2000)	
Difficulty in understanding the lessons and procrastinating in studying mathematics.				
Feeling frustrated when unable to solve problems. Yet, being happy when solutions are found and gained.				
Finding mathematics engaging at times, but occasionally feeling uncomfortable when struggling to understand concepts.				
Experiencing stress during impromptu problem-solving during board works.				
Encountering breakdown during unannounced quizzes.				
Diminished motivation and engagement in learning mathematics	Feeling disinterested during Math lessons and discussions.			
	Losing confidence in studying due to difficulties in understanding the lesson.			
	Feeling disinterested during problem-solving activities and preferring collaborative works.			
	Lack of interest during discussions, leading to			

	inattentiveness during discussion.			
	Having a mindset that mathematics is difficult.		Lack of motivation	
	Being challenged to change perception that mathematics is easy.			
Difficulties in applying mathematical knowledge and problem-solving strategies	Being challenged to memorize formulas	when	Difficulty with	Challenges with
	calculators are not allowed during assessments.		Memorizing	Mathematics
	Losing focus during mathematics due to frequent interruptions or questions from peers.		Formulas	Concepts and Skills
	Struggling with mathematics due to poor memorization skills, particularly with formulas which are essential in the subject.			
	Experiencing difficulties in grasping tricky mathematical concepts, leading to confusion.		Perceived	Constructivism
	Encountering various challenges in learning mathematics, including criticism from others.		difficulty of	Theory
	Having poor memorization skills as mathematics heavily relies on memorizing formulas.		mathematics	(Piaget, 1964)

Encountering Cognitive Challenges. In the context of mathematics anxiety, some experiences experienced by the students are cognitive challenges as well as difficulty understanding concepts. It was mentioned by the participants that experiencing anxiety which affects their performance, it can hinder their learning which led them to experience uncomfortable learning in mathematics.

Difficulty understanding concepts. This is the first code of the probed on the first probed issue. Students expressed common responses to learning math in the academic context. Most of them stated that they struggle to comprehend complex mathematical ideas, which can hinder their progress and cause confusion.

Similarly, the participant acknowledged the cognitive challenges faced while learning mathematics. The student expressed experiencing feelings of confusion and being overwhelmed, suggesting difficulties in understanding mathematical concepts. This highlights the importance of recognizing and addressing such emotional and cognitive barriers in the learning process. As Participant 1 said that:

"Sometimes feeling confused and overwhelmed while learning mathematics." (IDI-01)

Similarly, the cognitive challenges faced in understanding mathematical concepts. The student desired to review the material but struggled to recall the discussions due to the accumulation of lessons, leading to forgetfulness of problem-solving approaches and formulas. This highlights the difficulty in retaining and applying mathematical knowledge effectively. As Participant 3 said that:

"Gusto ko magreview pero makalimot ko sa discussion tungod kay magabot-abot ang mga lesson kana gud na moment mao na makalimot ko unsaon to ang pamaagi sa paganswer unsaon na pagsolve, unsa tung mga formula" (IDI-03)

(I want to review, but I forget the discussions because the lessons pile up, and you forget how to answer, how to solve, and what formulas to use.)

In addition, the confusion in comprehending mathematical concepts, citing the struggle to identify the source or origin of solutions. This highlights the difficulty in understanding the underlying reasoning and problem-solving approaches, which can hinder effective learning. The lack of clarity and guidance in solving mathematical problems contributes to this confusion. As Participant 7 said that:

"Kanang libog pud sya sabton usahay kay wala nami kung asa kuhaon ang solution asa gikan" (IDI-07)

(It is also confusing sometimes because we do not know where to get the solution from.)

Moreover, cognitive challenges faced in understanding difficult lessons, attributing it to the perceived limitations of their brain's capacity to grasp the material easily. This underscores the importance of recognizing individual differences and tailoring instructional approaches to facilitate better comprehension. The complexity of the material often overwhelms students, making it difficult for them to keep up. As Participant 10 said that:

"I really have a hard time because some of the lessons are so hard to understand and the capacity of my brain to understand that lesson is not really that smart enough to understand it easily." (IDI-10)

Furthermore, students perceived difficulty in mathematics especially when answering questions on the board. This highlights the potential impact of assessment methods and performance pressure on students' learning experiences and comprehension. The anxiety associated with public problem-solving can significantly affect a student's confidence and understanding. As Participant 14 said that:

"Makaingon ko na lisod ang math or maganswer ug mathematics labaw na ug paansweron mi sa board" (IDI-14)

(I can say that math is difficult or answering mathematics questions, especially when we have to answer on the board.)

Personal Struggles with Problem-solving. This is the second code of the first probed issue. IDI participants highlight the difficulties

students face in applying mathematical knowledge to solve problems. First-year students expressed various challenges related to problem-solving, such as struggling to keep up with discussions, identifying appropriate strategies, and executing solutions correctly.

Similarly, the challenges faced during exams or quizzes, highlighting the need for advanced studying and self-reliance in problem-solving. The participant recognized the importance of learning mathematics despite the difficulties, as it is crucial to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills. The pressure to perform well in mathematics assessments can be overwhelming but also serves as a motivation to study harder. As Participant 1 said that:

"So akong challenges kung naay ano exam or naay quizzes is magadvance study ko ug magsalig ko sa akong kaugalingon na kaya nako and then aron challenge jud sa math is matawag sya na challenges tungod kay magsolve-solve and then okay pud sya para sa akoa kay mas importante man gyud na naa tay malearn so dapat gyud na kailangan gyud sya tun-an" (IDI-01)

(My challenge when there are exams or quizzes is that I study in advance and rely on myself that I can do it, and then the challenge in math is called a challenge because of solving problems, but it is okay for me because it is important that we learn, so we really need to study it.

Moreover, the feeling of being pressured and anxious during problem-solving experiences, coupled with the excitement of knowing how to answer but overthinking the possibility of making mistakes. This highlights the emotional and cognitive challenges students face when attempting to solve mathematical problems. The fear of making even a minor error can overshadow their confidence and problem-solving abilities. As Participant 4 said that:

"Nakafeel ko ug kapressure, kakulba na excitement when we say excitement, feel nako kay kabalo ko moanswer pero magoverthink ko nga biskan pag unsa na kataas imong pagsolve sa math pero kang naa ra gihapon mamali na 1 number – IDI 04"

(I feel pressured, that anxious excitement when we say experience of excitement, that is how I feel because I know how to answer, but I overthink that no matter how high you solve in math, there is still a chance of making a mistake with one number.)

In addition, the difficulty of mathematics, particularly in problem-solving, emphasizing the challenges of keeping up with discussions and understanding the source or origin of solutions. This underscores the importance of effective communication and guidance in facilitating problem-solving skills. Without clear explanations, students can feel lost and unable to follow along. As Participant 7 said that:

"Lisod jud ang math, labi na sa problem solving nga usahay dili dayon labi nag magdiscuss tapos dili dayon namo macatch up ang gipangngon ni sir, libog pud sya sabton usahay kay wala nami kabalo kung asa ang solution gikan" (IDI-07)

(Math is really difficult, especially with problem-solving, where sometimes we do not immediately catch up with what the teacher is discussing, and it's also confusing sometimes because we do not know where to get the solution from.)

Furthermore, the disappointment and negative emotions experienced when being unprepared and unable to answer a question, expressing the desire to not change this factor despite the associated shame and disappointment. This sheds light on the emotional impact of unpreparedness and the need for effective support systems to address such challenges. Being unable to answer questions can significantly affect students' self-esteem and motivation. As Participant 10 stated:

"Kanang tawagon ko tapos wala koy matubag kay within unprepared kay wala lagi ko naminaw kana na factor dili gyud nako na sya gusto mausab kay aside sa ulaw lain pud sa feeling kay dako kaayo sya'g disappointment sa akong kaugalingon kay wala nako naansweran, wala nako sya nahibal-an" (IDI-10)

(When I was called on and I cannot answer because I am unprepared since I did not listen, that is a factor I do not want to change because aside from the shame, it is a different feeling, a great disappointment in myself because you could not answer it, I did not know it.)

Additionally, the student described the challenges of taking a long time to solve problems and sometimes not being able to find the exact answer, even after extended effort. This highlights the importance of developing perseverance and effective problem-solving strategies to overcome such obstacles. The difficulties in reaching solutions can be discouraging and may require additional support. As Participant 11 said that:

"Ang challenges dugay gyud sya mahuman ug answer mao gyud na sya, dugay ko makahuman ug answer nya naa pud time na kapuyon na lang ko'g solve nya wala gihapon nako nakuha ang exact na tubag or answer" (IDI-11)

(The challenge is that it takes a long time to complete and get the answer, you take a long time to finish answering, and there are times when you get tired of solving but still don't get the exact answer.)

Lastly, the challenges faced in solving mathematical problems, emphasizing the difficulties encountered during the learning process. This underscores the need for effective instructional strategies and support systems to address these problem-solving challenges. These difficulties often lead to frustration and can hinder academic progress. As Participant 14 said that:

"The challenges that I perceived during learning mathematics is especially the part that makaencounter ug difficulties in solving

mathematics” (IDI-14)

(The challenges I perceived during learning mathematics are especially the part where I encounter difficulties in solving mathematics.)

Lack of understanding. This is the third code of the first probed issue. IDI participants shared that they face significant cognitive challenges, particularly in understanding complex mathematical concepts. The lack of clear explanations and the inherent difficulty of the subject matter contribute to their struggles in grasping these topics. This indicates a crucial need for enhanced instructional methods and additional support to facilitate better comprehension among students.

Similarly, Participant 1 recognized the cognitive challenges associated with understanding complex mathematical concepts. The participant expressed difficulty and confusion when learning mathematics, highlighting the need for clearer explanations to aid comprehension. This underscores the significant challenge of grasping abstract ideas without adequate instructional support. As Participant 1 said that:

"I've seen some difficulties in grasping tricky math like ideas like maglisod jud ko when it comes mathematics, and sometimes feeling confused and overwhelmed while learning." (IDI-01)

"I have experienced difficulties grasping complex mathematical concepts, often struggling with mathematics and sometimes feeling confused and overwhelmed while learning."

Moreover, the lack of clear explanations during math lessons poses a significant challenge for students, as noted by Participant 3. The participant described struggles with understanding and solving problems without proper guidance, which underscores the necessity for thorough and effective teaching methods. This highlights the importance of clear communication in the learning process to overcome cognitive barriers. As Participant 3 said that:

"So dili lang na nacrítisize kundi kanang challenges pud sa akua kana gud the moment na magtuon ko ug math math na walay explain ug tarong sa akua mao pud na akong usa sa mga maglisod pud ko ug kanang pagsabot sa problems or unsaon pagsolve ana na problem." (IDI-03)

"Not only have I faced criticism, but also challenges during the times I study math without proper explanations. This has made it difficult for me to understand the problems and figure out how to solve them."

In addition, a student shared that freshmen year presented significant challenges in understanding mathematics due to the difficulty of the lessons. The participant noted the struggle to keep up with the material and felt that their cognitive capacity was insufficient for grasping the concepts easily. This emphasizes the need for tailored educational approaches that consider the varying cognitive capabilities of students. As Participant 10 said that:

"Based on my experience as a first-year student, the challenges I face in mathematics include difficulty keeping up with lessons. Some of the material is very hard to understand, and I often feel that my ability to grasp these concepts is not sufficient to comprehend them easily." (IDI-10)

Furthermore, the student highlighted that certain areas of mathematics require intense focus and attention due to their complexity. The participant emphasized the necessity of dedicating significant effort to understand challenging mathematical parts, indicating that some topics inherently demand more cognitive resources. This reveals that persistent and targeted practice is essential for mastering difficult subjects. As Participant 14 said that:

"Mga challenges na pareha sa usahay dili gyud kaayo ikalimod na naa gyud part sa math na biskan need gyud kaayo sya ug kailangan gyud nako sya pagtuonan ug ug pansin kay lisod gyud kaayo sabton like kana nga challenges na akong naencounter." (IDI-14)

"Challenges like those where sometimes you just cannot forget that there is a part of math that seems really essential, and I really need to focus on it and pay attention because it is really difficult to understand, challenges like that I have encountered."

Experiencing Emotional and Psychological Crises. In response to the in-depth interviews, participants highlighted the significant emotional and psychological challenges they face in learning mathematics. These challenges include anxiety, fear of making mistakes, discomfort, frustration, and stress. These factors profoundly affect students' engagement and performance in their math classes.

Having Mathematical Anxiety. This is the first code for the second probed issue. From the in-depth interviews, anxiety in learning math emerges as a prevalent concern among the participants, manifesting as feelings of panic, pressure, and fear during math-related activities. Participants described experiencing anxiety particularly when faced with challenging math problems or oral assessments, highlighting the psychological burden associated with mathematical learning. This anxiety not only affects their performance but also creates a sense of dread and apprehension, hindering their ability to focus and engage effectively in learning activities.

Similarly, a significant level of anxiety related to mathematics affects their interest and engagement in the subject. The participant noted that their level of interest fluctuates based on their understanding of the topic, highlighting a clear correlation between comprehension and motivation. This underscores the importance of addressing anxiety to enhance students' engagement and learning in mathematics. As participant 1 said that:

"I feel like so disinterested but if maganahan ko sa topic or magets dayon nako ang point kay ganahan rako maminaw pero sometimes it's make me feel panic jud kay naa jud ko anxiety sa mathematics." (IDI-01)

"I often feel disinterested, but if I become interested in the topic or quickly grasp the point, I enjoy listening. However, sometimes it causes me to feel anxious because I experience anxiety with mathematics."

Moreover, the pressure of studying mathematics, especially when dealing with complex numerical problems, was a recurring theme among participants. A student described the experience as overwhelming, leading to confusion and a loss of focus due to the sheer volume and difficulty of the tasks. This highlights how anxiety can impede cognitive functions and affect academic performance. As Participant 2 said that:

"Pressure kaayo, hassle bitaw kaayo, kay magstudy ko is number man jud tanan pareha anang dili, dili kayko makasabot ug mga numbers maayo untag gagmay lang kay usahay daghan nman kaayo ba murag libog dili kaayo nako macalculate ug taong murag malibog ko'g maayo hangtod sa murag mawala na sa focus." (IDI-02)

"The pressure is intense, it feels very burdensome because studying revolves entirely around numbers, which can be difficult to comprehend. It would be better if they were simpler, as sometimes there are so many numbers that it becomes confusing and I cannot calculate properly, causing me to lose focus.

Additionally, the student articulated a fear of failure that accompanies quizzes and exams in mathematics, which exacerbates their anxiety. The participant highlighted the stress of potentially getting wrong answers despite extensive study, particularly when expected topics do not appear in exams. This emphasizes the need for strategies to manage exam-related anxiety to improve student well-being and performance. As Participant 4 said that:

"Especially kung magklase sa math, then diba magquiz ang teacher molecture pa man gyud sya, mga 5 minutes magtuon ko ana before magquiz ang teacher mahadlok ko kung magquiz na, mahadlok ko na mamali, mali ba akong answer or tama kay hinaguan pud baya nimo na magtuon ko ana, and especially atong pagexam kay kato man gud ginastudihan namo kay wala nanggawas sa exam." (IDI-04)

"Especially when we have classes in mathematics and then the teacher would give a quiz even after lecturing, so I only have about 5 minutes to review before the quiz starts. I feel anxious when it's time for the quiz, afraid of making mistakes and unsure if my answers are correct, because it's challenging to study within that limited time frame. And especially during exams, because what we studied may not even appear on the exam."

Furthermore, the anxiety experienced during mathematics classes was particularly pronounced during activities involving board work or oral presentations, as described by Participant 10. The participant expressed a fear of being unable to answer questions in front of the class, which heightens their anxiety levels. This reflects the broader impact of performance anxiety on students' classroom experiences and underscores the need for supportive learning environments. As Participant 10 said that:

"Every naay sa amoang math period makafeel ko ug anxiety especially kanang naay mga board work or naay oral na pagahimuon. Makafeel ko ug anxiety kay fear of nothing to able to answer in front of the class." (IDI-10)

"Every time in our math period, I experience anxiety, especially when there are board works or oral recitations. I feel anxious because of the fear of not being able to answer in front of the class."

Fear of making mistakes and being judged. This is the second code for the second probed issue. The fear of making mistakes or being judged for not understanding quickly can create a sense of inadequacy and hinder students' willingness to engage with mathematical concepts. Participants highlighted that a significant barrier to effective learning in mathematics is the fear of making mistakes and being judged. This fear manifests in various ways, from struggling to grasp key concepts to feeling pressured by exams and grades.

Similarly, the fear of being judged for not understanding new concepts quickly is a major stressor. Unlike other subjects, where they might grasp ideas more readily, mathematics often requires more time and effort to understand, which can lead to anxiety and a lack of enjoyment in learning. As Participant 1 stated:

"Akoang undesirable experience in learning mathematics kay struggling to understand key concepts, experiencing a feeling pressured by exams and grades, and dealing with a fear of making mistakes or being judged for not understanding quickly because it takes time for me to understand a new concepts unlike sa uban subject nga dali ra nako masabtan that's why I can't enjoy in learning mathematics." (IDI-01)

("My undesirable experience in learning mathematics includes struggling to understand key concepts, feeling pressured by exams and grades, and dealing with a fear of making mistakes or being judged for not understanding quickly because it takes me time to understand new concepts, unlike other subjects that I can easily grasp. That is why I cannot enjoy learning mathematics.")

Furthermore, the feeling of fear of criticism from peers can further exacerbate this anxiety. The Participant expressed that being criticized for not understanding a problem can be demoralizing, especially when unsure how to approach or solve it. This highlights the importance of supportive learning environments where students feel comfortable seeking help and guidance. As Participant 3 said:

"Kanang icriticize ka tungod kay ang tao mura naa man gud, kung baga ang tao wala niya nasabtan kana na problem tungod kay wala pud sya kasabot unsaon paghandle or unsaon pag answer na kana na problem ing ana gud, so need gyud nato sabton ang usa ka tao ing ana gud, if ever man na mamali sya imo tudluan ug unsay angay buhaton, unsay pamaagi ug unsay way". (IDI-03)

("Being criticized because the person doesn't understand the problem and does not know how to handle or solve it, that is how it is. So, we really need to understand the person. If ever they make a mistake, you teach them what should be done, the method, and the way.")

Additionally, the experience of being called to answer questions orally in class can also be a significant source of anxiety. The fear of going blank or being unable to answer questions in front of peers can be overwhelming. This illustrates the intense pressure students feel during such situations, impacting their ability to concentrate and perform effectively. As participant 4 said that:

"When magpaoral ang teacher kay mobati ko'g kakulba tapos mablanko akong utok. Mablanko akong utok tapos pangsington ka ug kung magtuon ko ug math kay di ko kafocus especially sa akong mga klasmit na mga samukan o mga disturbo." (IDI-04)

("When the teacher asks oral questions, I feel nervous, then my mind goes blank. My mind goes blank, and I start sweating. When I study math, I cannot focus, especially with my classmates who are noisy or distracting.")

Lastly, being unprepared for a question and failing to answer it in front of the class can lead to feelings of embarrassment and self-disappointment. It emphasizes the importance of creating supportive learning environments where students feel comfortable asking questions and seeking clarification without fear of judgment. This highlights the emotional toll of being unprepared and the internal struggle students face when unable to respond to questions in class. As Participant 10 said that:

"Kanang tawagon ko tapos kanang wala kay matubag kay within unprepared kay wala lagi ka naminaw kana na factor dili gyud nako na sya gusto mausab kay aside sa ulaw kanang murag lain pud sa feeling kay kanang, kanang dako kaayo sya'g disappointment sa imong kaugalingon kay wala nimo sya naansweran, wala nimo sya nahibal-an." (IDI-10)

("When I was called and I do not have an answer because I were unprepared and didn't listen, that is a factor I do not want to happen again. Aside from the embarrassment, it feels bad because it is a big disappointment in myself for not being able to answer or know it.")

Building Positive Attitude from Negative Emotions. This is the third code of the second probed issue. Participants expressed that their journey to building a positive attitude often starts from acknowledging and transforming their negative emotions related to learning, particularly in mathematics.

Similarly, the commitment for improving in math despite finding it difficult and uncomfortable. These emphasized a determination to overcome these negative feelings by gradually working to enhance their math skills. This attitude highlights the importance of perseverance in the face of academic challenges. As Participant 1 said that:

"Sometimes lang, but even if it's difficult and boring. Even if it makes me feel uncomfortable. I'll do my best to become better at math so that maimprove pa nako sya in the future so mahinay hinayan na ko syag improve." (IDI-01)

(Sometimes, but even if it's difficult and boring. Even if it makes me feel uncomfortable, I will do my best to become better at math so that I can improve it in the future, and I will gradually work on improving it.)

Additionally, the initial self-doubt they experience before attempting a task, particularly in math. Despite feeling incapable at first, they often find that they can accomplish the task once they try. This reflection points to the significance of self-belief and the impact of self-perception on learning outcomes. As Participant 2 said:

"Kanang feeling sa akua na dili gani ko, feeling sa akong self dili na ko kaya pero makaya ra diay murag ginadown una nako akong sarili ba before nako itry." (IDI-02)

(The feeling that I cannot do it, but then realizing that I actually can. It is like I put myself down before even trying.)

Furthermore, the discomfort in learning math due to differing teaching methods and a personal tendency to procrastinate. However, they acknowledged that this discomfort is occasional, indicating that their engagement with the subject can vary based on these factors. These emphasized the importance of finding effective strategies to overcome these challenges and maintain consistent engagement with mathematics. As Participant 4 stated:

"Diili ko comfortable sa math kay naa man gud uban teacher na lahi ilang pamaagi sa pagtudlo dili ko kacatch up kaayo and some reason is tapolan pud ko motuon ug math pero usahay ra." (IDI-04)

(I am not comfortable with math because some teachers have different teaching methods that I cannot catch up with, and sometimes it is because I am lazy to study math, but it is just sometimes.)

Moreover, the range of emotions they experience while learning mathematics, from frustration when unable to find the answer to happiness when succeed. This emotional rollercoaster illustrates the intense personal investment and the significant emotional impact of the learning process. Additionally, it highlighted the need for effective coping mechanisms to manage these intense emotions and

maintain motivation in their mathematical endeavors. As Participant 9 stated:

"While learning mathematics is daghan gyud ko mafeel, first is dili nako makuha ang answer malagot ko, maglagot gyud ko basta dili nako makuha ang answer kay para pud sa akoo lisod kaayo pangitaon ang answer na lisod kaayo ang question tapos mao na makafeel ko ug anger, murag anger issues gani then aside pud ana is happy ko basta masolve or makuha nako ang answer sa sakong question." (IDI-09)

(While learning mathematics, I feel many things. First, when I cannot get the answer, I get angry because it is really hard to find the answer to a difficult question. But then, I also feel happy when I solve or get the answer to the question.)

Lastly, while finding that mathematics is engaging and consider it one of their favorite subjects, it will occasionally feel uncomfortable when it takes a long time to grasp certain concepts. This duality of finding the subject both engaging and occasionally challenging underscores the complex relationship students can have with math. As Participant 14 said that:

"Dili ko komportable ug math is time something na dili gyud kaayo nako experience nako na katong dugay kaayo nako sya nagets pero I find it mathematics engaging murag mao pud ni sya pud ang kanang isa sa akong mga favorite subject pero mao nang talagsa lang pud ko mafeel if uncomfortable while learning mathematics." (IDI-14)

(I am not comfortable with math sometimes, especially when it takes me a long time to understand something. But I find mathematics engaging, and it is one of my favorite subjects, so I rarely feel uncomfortable while learning it.)

Feeling Stress During Discussion. This is the third code for the second probed issue. The participants experiencing stress during discussions is a common challenge among participants, often leading to frustration, anxiety, and a sense of helplessness. The stress particularly arises in situations involving problem-solving tasks that participants find difficult to solve, impromptu questions, and unexpected quizzes. This stress not only impacts their ability to think clearly but also diminishes their confidence and willingness to participate in discussions.

In connection with that, students described a pervasive sense of frustration when unable to solve a problem, which significantly contributes to their stress levels. This feeling of frustration stems from the natural desire to successfully resolve problems and the disappointment of not being able to do so. As Participant 10 said that:

"Permanente man siguro kanang every naay problem solving nya dili nako sya kaya isolve kay mafrustrate jud ko kay syempre kinsa may ganahan anang dili nimo masolve ang isa ka problem so perme gyud ko mafrustrate." (IDI-10)

("Probably every time there is problem-solving and I cannot solve it, I really get frustrated because, of course, who would want not to solve a problem, so I am always frustrated.")

Additionally, the pressure of impromptu problem-solving sessions intensifies the stress experienced by participants. The participant shared that the stress becomes particularly acute when they are given a problem to solve on the spot with a strict time limit. The lack of preparation time and the presence of monitoring exacerbate their difficulty in managing the task. The participant stated:

"Sometimes makacause sya ug stress sa akoo labaw na ug kanang impromptu like for example hatagan mo ug problem tapos ikaw na bahala kana ganing answer sa problem tapos hatagan mo ug 5 minutes tapos impromptu gyud dili nang kanang ginabantyan gyud mo diraa gyud ko maglisod." (IDI-12)

("Sometimes it causes me stress, especially during impromptu situations like when you're given a problem and you have to solve it within 5 minutes while being monitored, I really struggle with that.")

Moreover, unexpected quizzes can lead to severe stress and anxiety, as described by Participant 14. The participant recounted a particular instance where an unannounced quiz on an unfamiliar topic resulted in an overwhelming sense of stress, nearly causing a breakdown. This highlights how sudden academic demands can significantly affect students' emotional well-being. As Participant 14 said that:

"Actually po kato pud one time kay nakaencounter gyud ko mga feelings like nastress gyud kaayo ko ato kay nagpakalit ug quiz ang among instructor and then wala ko complete knowledge ato na topic like abrupt kaayo na quiz then pagkahuman ato wala gyud ko kadea-idea if unsaon to murag nagbreakdown ko, kahilakon na gyud kaayo ko kay wala gyud ko kabalo ba unsaon gyud to sya paganswer like nagtungang tanan nako stress and anxiety kay like hala unsaon mani sya pagsolve nagahatag si teacher ug time lang para masolve namo to and then wala gyud ko kaidea-idea if unsaon to sya." (IDI-14)

("Actually, there was one time I really felt stressed because our instructor gave a surprise quiz, and I had no complete knowledge on the topic. It was such an abrupt quiz, and I had no idea how to answer it, I almost had a breakdown and felt like crying because I really did not know how to solve it. The stress and anxiety all came together because the teacher gave us time to solve it, but I had no idea how to do it.")

Lack of Motivation and Interest. In response to the in-depth interviews, the participants mentioned experiencing a lack of motivation and interest in their studies, particularly in subjects they find challenging. This lack of motivation manifests as disinterest and a lack of

confidence, significantly impacting their engagement and performance in these subjects.

Being Disinterested with Math Class. The first code of the third probed issue. Many of the participants expressed various experiences regarding their disinterest in math class, often attributing it to feelings of anxiety, lack of confidence, and the exhausting nature of problem-solving tasks. These highlight the multifaceted reasons behind students' disengagement with mathematics.

Similarly, the conveyed feeling of both disinterest and anxiety about mathematics indicates a correlation between disinterest and anxiety within the subject. The participant acknowledged the challenge but expressed determination to improve their math skills for the future, despite feeling uncomfortable. This highlights the internal conflict between a desire for self-improvement and the anxiety that hinders it. As Participant said that:

"Sometimes lang, but even if it's difficult and boring. Even if it makes me feel uncomfortable. I'll do my best to become better at math so that maimprove pa nako sya in the future so mahinay-hinayan na ko syag improve." (IDI-01)

(Sometimes, even if it is difficult and boring, even if it makes me feel uncomfortable, I'll do my best to become better at math so that I can improve in the future and gradually get better.)

Moreover, the detrimental impact of their lack of confidence on their approach to studying math, often leading to a neglect of the subject. The statement underscores how a lack of belief in one's abilities can significantly affect academic performance and overall engagement. This reveals a cycle where disinterest leads to avoidance, further diminishing confidence and performance. As Participant 2 said that:

"Kanang wala pud kay confident mostudy kay murag hunahuna nako, ay d man gihapon ko kabalo ani, usahay murag baliwalaon na lng nimo ang subject." (IDI- 02)

(I do not have the confidence to study because I think, 'I do not know this anyway,' so sometimes I just neglect the subject.)

In addition, the exhausting and uninteresting nature of problem-solving tasks in math class, particularly when tackled individually. The participant expressed a preference for collaborative learning, indicating the importance of support systems in navigating challenging academic tasks. This preference suggests that group work might mitigate some of the stress and disinterest experienced in individual problem-solving. As Participant 13 said that:

"Exhausting and uninterested in a way na naay problem solving na involved sa ginahatag na set sa instructor mafeel nako ug naay ginahatag na problem set ang instructor like lisod gyud sya sa akoo especially kung individual kay mas prefer ko ug I have someone na motabang sa akoo na sabton ang problem po naa koy kabrainstorming sa topic." (IDI-13)

(Exhausting and uninterested in a way that involves problem-solving tasks given by the instructor. I find it really difficult, especially when done individually. I prefer having someone to help me understand and brainstorm the problem.)

Furthermore, the disruptive effect of disinterest on their ability to focus during math class discussions. These attributed their disinterest in finding the topic boring and expressed how it affects their attention and engagement during lessons. This suggests that enhancing the interest level of the subject matter could improve focus and participation. As Participant 5 said that:

"Wala ko gana sa math tapos dako jud sya epekto sa akong grado sa math kay kining ang topic bitaw kay boring tapos dili ko ganahan maminaw di gyud nako mapugngan tapos kana bang katulugon ko tas wala na ko pokus maminaw mao d na ko ganahan during sa discussion." (IDI-05)

(I have no interest in math, and it greatly affects my grade because the topic is boring, and I do not like listening. I cannot help but feel sleepy, and I lose focus, which makes me dislike the discussion even more.)

Lack of Motivation. The second code of the third probed issue. Participants expressed various reasons for their lack of motivation in learning mathematics, primarily due to difficulty in understanding key concepts, pressure from exams, fear of making mistakes, and being judged by peers.

In that sense, the undesirable experience in learning mathematics highlights the struggle to understand key concepts and the pressure from exams and grades. These noted that the fear of making mistakes and being judged for not understanding quickly contributes to their lack of enjoyment in learning mathematics. This reflects a broader issue where the pressure to perform well and quickly grasp new concepts can significantly diminish students' motivation. As Participant 14 said that:

"Akoang undesirable experience in learning mathematics kay struggling to understand key concepts, experiencing a feeling pressured by exams and grades, and dealing with a fear of making mistakes or being judged for not understanding quickly because it takes time for me to understand a new concepts unlike sa uban subject nga dali ra nako masabtan that's why I can't enjoy in learning mathematics." (IDI-01)

(My undesirable experience in learning mathematics includes struggling to understand key concepts, feeling pressured by exams and grades, and dealing with a fear of making mistakes or being judged for not understanding quickly because it takes me time to understand new concepts, unlike in other subjects that I can easily grasp. That is why I cannot enjoy learning mathematics.)

Additionally, the impact of being judged by peers on their motivation to learn math. The participant expressed how judgment from others, especially in this generation, discourages them and lowers their self-esteem. This judgmental attitude from peers can create a hostile learning environment, further demotivating students who are already struggling. As Participant 3 said that:

"Kanang ijudge ka kay naay mga student karon na generation murag gijudge ka ba porket wala ka kabalo ana na answer or porket wala ka kabalo ana kana gud unsaon na pagsolve ana na problem e judge ka ingnan dayon ka na bugo." (IDI-03)

(The feeling of being judged by peers because some students nowadays tend to judge you if you do not know the answer or how to solve a problem. They immediately label you as dumb.)

Moreover, the impact of preconceived notions and self-imposed standards on their motivation to study math. The participant acknowledged that viewing math as inherently difficult has become a significant challenge. This mindset not only makes it hard to like math but also to change their negative perception of the subject, resulting in a persistent lack of motivation. As Participant 13 said that:

"Siguro katong nagset ko ug standards or ginaset nako sa akong mind na ang math is lisod sguro kana na challenge sa akoa because na tungod ana na ano nako mindset is murag feel nako mas isod nako baguhon sya or lisod nako, lisod ko mag... tawag ana uy malike ang math tungod sa akong mindset na lisod ang math kay ako mismo wala ko gatuo na naay sayon sa math." (IDI- 13)

(Probably because I set standards or have this mindset that math is difficult, which challenges me. Because of this mindset, I feel like it's harder for me to change it or to like math because I do not believe that there is anything easy about math.)

Lastly, lack of interest in math, noting that the boring nature of certain topics and their difficulty focusing during discussions significantly impact their grades. This statement highlights how disengagement can directly affect academic performance. These emphasized the need for more engaging teaching methods to spark interest and improve focus during class discussions. As Participant 5 said that:

"Wala koy gana sa math kay tapos dako jud sya epekto sa akong grado sa math kay ang topic bitaw kay boring tapos dili ko ganahan maminaw di gyud nako mapugngan tapos kana bang katulugon ko tas wala na ko pokus maminaw mao d na ko ganahan during sa discussion." (IDI-05)

(I have no interest in math because it significantly affects my grades. The topic is boring, and I do not like listening, so I cannot help but feel sleepy and lose focus, which makes me dislike the discussion.)

Challenges with Mathematics Concepts and Skills. In response to the in- depth interviews and focus group discussions, participants highlighted several challenges they face with mathematics concepts and skills. A common theme that emerged was the difficulty in memorizing formulas, maintaining focus during lessons, and dealing with unfamiliar mathematical concepts. These challenges collectively contribute to the students' struggles with effectively learning and applying mathematical principles.

Difficulty with formulas and memorization. This is the first code for the fourth probed issue. A significant challenge highlighted by the participants is the difficulty in memorizing mathematical formulas. Students expressed that when teachers require assessments without the use of calculators, it necessitates the memorization of numerous formulas, which many find overwhelming. This issue is compounded for students who struggle with memorization, making mathematics particularly daunting. As Participant 9 said that:

"Daghan gyud pero ang main kay ano jud kanang moingon ang teacher na kuntahay magassessment tapos moingon sila na no calculator allowed tapos magmemorize sa formula" (IDI-09)

(There are many, but the main issue is when the teacher says there will be an assessment and that no calculators are allowed, and we have to memorize the formulas.)

In addition, the need for focused attention during mathematics lessons is crucial, as interruptions can significantly affect a student's ability to concentrate and retain information. The participant noted that constant questioning during math tasks disrupts their focus, hindering their learning process. The interruptions can lead to frustration and decreased comprehension. As Participant 8 said that:

"Ang akoang isa gyud kay kana gud naay sige'g pangutana while gabuhat sa math kay ako man basta gapaminaw ko maminaw lang sa gyud ko pero makawala man gud kanang focus kay daghan kaayo si'g pangutana mao na akong isa sa assessment." (IDI- 08)

(One of my issues is when there are constant questions while doing math because when I listen, I just want to listen, but it disrupts my focus since there are too many questions. That is one of my issues during assessments.)

Furthermore, unfamiliarity with certain mathematical concepts contributes to the difficulty in learning mathematics. The participant indicated that some lessons covered in class were either not previously encountered or not sufficiently familiar, adding to their struggles. This unfamiliarity can create a gap in understanding, making it harder for students to keep up with the curriculum. As Participant 12 said that:

"For me ang math is very hard for me gyud kay daghan ug mga lessons na wala o dili kaayo mafamiliarize nako kay ana ni teacher naa daw na sya before." (IDI-12)

(For me, math is very hard because there are many lessons that I am not or not very familiar with because the teacher said it was covered before.)

Moreover, a general aversion to mathematics due to its reliance on memorization further exacerbates the difficulties faced by students. Those with poor memorization skills find mathematics particularly challenging, as the subject often requires the retention of various formulas and concepts. This aversion can lead to a lack of motivation and confidence in tackling mathematical problems. As Participant 13 said that:

“Dili kaayo ko into math na subject para sa akua lisod ang math most especially sa akua na naay poor memorization samot na math is more on memorizing formula.” (IDI-13)

(I am not really into math as a subject. For me, math is hard, especially because I have poor memorization skills, and math is more about memorizing formulas.)

Lastly, the significant challenge in understanding mathematics is the lack of foundational knowledge, which hinders the ability to memorize and apply formulas. Participants noted that while they can grasp mathematical problems conceptually, the difficulty arises when recalling specific formulas necessary for problem-solving. This highlights the importance of reinforcing foundational skills and memorization techniques to improve overall mathematical proficiency. As Participant 11 said that:

“Kanang mga formula na wala or dili gani familiar sa akua dili pud ko dali makamemorize ug mga formula mao na akong hate sa math, dali ko makasabot sa problem, ang problema lang gyud is unsaon nako sya paganswer kung wala ko kamemorize sa formula.” (IDI-12)

(Those formulas that are not familiar to me, I cannot easily memorize them, that's why I hate math. I can understand the problem quickly, but the problem is how to solve it if I have not memorized the formula.)

Perceived difficulty of mathematics. The second code of the fourth probed issue. It is a notable concern among students, significantly affecting their learning experience. Students often find themselves grappling with complex mathematical ideas, which leads to feelings of confusion and being overwhelmed. This perception of difficulty is not only due to the challenging nature of the subject but also due to the lack of confidence in their abilities. As Participant 1 noted that:

“So as a student, I've seen some difficulties in grasping tricky math like ideas like maglisod jud ko when it comes mathematics, and sometimes feeling confused and overwhelmed while learning” (IDI-01)

(As a student, I have seen some difficulties in grasping tricky math ideas. I find it hard when it comes to mathematics and sometimes feel confused and overwhelmed while learning.)

In addition, the challenges encountered during mathematics learning are often exacerbated by external criticism, which can further diminish a student's confidence. This criticism can come from peers, or even family members, compounding the student's anxiety and reluctance to engage with the subject. The Participant highlighted the impact of being criticized while trying to learn, which adds to the stress and difficulty of the subject. As Participant 3 expressed that:

“Sa akua is daghan jud kaayo mga challenges na akong naencounter sa pagtuon sa mathematics like naay mocritisize saimoha” (IDI-03)

(For me, there are really many challenges that I encounter in studying mathematics like being criticized.)

Moreover, students who are not inherently inclined towards mathematics find the subject particularly daunting due to its reliance on memorization, especially of formulas. This reliance can create a significant barrier for those who struggle with retaining information, ultimately hindering their ability to solve mathematical problems effectively. Poor memorization skills can make mathematics seem even more insurmountable, leading to a lack of engagement and increased difficulty in mastering the subject. As Participant 13 mentioned that:

“Ang akoang difficulties while learning mathematics is that maglisod ko ug engage sa math its because dili kaayo ko into math na subject para sa akua lisod ang math most especially sa akua na naay poor memorization samot na math is more on memorizing formula” (IDI-13)

(My difficulties while learning mathematics are that I find it hard to engage in math because I am not really into the subject. For me, math is hard, especially since I have poor memorization skills, and math is more about memorizing formulas.)

Data Integration of the Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

The present study on the mathematics anxiety of first-year students in a local college carries out a mixed methods approach employing a convergent parallel approach. The third research question of the study involves the corroboration of the findings from the quantitative and qualitative phases. The table 5 on the salient quantitative and qualitative findings presents the focal points in the first column which contains the aspect or focal points of the study followed by the quantitative and qualitative findings in the second and third column. The findings from the quantitative phase are usually the indicators with the highest mean while the qualitative findings which display

the identified responses show confirmation or disconfirmation to the quantitative results. The fourth column is the nature of the data integration and the fifth column contains the axiological implications made based on the data described in the preceding columns.

Physical and emotional Factors. In the quantitative phase, the specific item under the indicator physical and emotional factors rated as high about experiencing emotional distress, including anger, crying, and extreme frustration, when confronted with math tasks. Also, the items about encountering difficulties in maintaining regular sleep patterns following the completion of math assignments or on nights preceding math-related events, suffering from headaches or neck stiffness when involved in mathematical thinking or activities, and feeling an accelerated heart rate during the execution of math-related tasks or contemplation of mathematical problems, are both rated as high. This result is connected with the qualitative findings on the category mathematical anxiety under the theme experiencing emotional and psychological crises. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges quantitative.

Assessment Factor. In the quantitative phase, the specific item under the indicator assessment factor rated as high about consistently performing below expectations on math tests compared to other subjects. Also, the items about feeling the need for more extensive preparation when studying for math tests than for tests in other subjects, encountering difficulty maintaining focus during math tests, characterized by racing thoughts and moments of mental blankness, and having a lack of confidence in my abilities during math tests, regardless of the thoroughness of my preparation, are both rated as high. This result is connected with the qualitative findings on the category of personal struggles with problem-solving under the theme of challenges with mathematics concepts and skills. Hence, the qualitative data converges quantitative in this aspect.

Social Factor. In the quantitative phase, the specific item under the indicator social factor rated as high about perceiving others to have a more mathematical or logical mind than I do. Also, the item about finding myself worrying about other people’s math abilities and comparing them to my own is rated as high. This result is connected with the qualitative findings on the category lack of motivation under the theme of lack of motivation and interest. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges quantitative.

Table 5. Joint Display of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

<i>Aspect Or Focal Point</i>	<i>Quantitative Findings</i>	<i>Qualitative Findings</i>	<i>Nature Of Data Integration</i>	<i>Axiological Implications</i>
Physical and Emotional Factors	Table 1 on the indicator of physical and emotional factors, specifically item 1 about experiencing emotional distress, including anger, crying, and extreme frustration, when confronted with math tasks (M=3.52), item 2 about encountering difficulties in maintaining regular sleep patterns following the completion of math assignments or on nights preceding math-related events (M=3.61), item 3 about suffering from headaches or neck stiffness when involved in mathematical thinking or activities (M=3.53), item 5 about feeling an accelerated heart rate during the execution of math-related tasks or contemplation of mathematical problems (M=3.47), all rated as high.	Table 3.3 core ideas- on the category - mathematical anxiety under the them - Experiencing emotional and psychological crises	Merging – converging	Students experience high physical and emotional stress related to math tasks, reflecting significant anxiety and psychological crises impacting their ability to perform and engage in math.
Assessment Factor	Table 2 on the indicator of assessment factors specifically item 1 about consistently performing below expectations on math tests compared to other subjects (M=3.64), item 2 about feeling the need for more extensive preparation when studying for math tests than for tests in other subjects (M=3.74), item 3 about encountering difficulty maintaining focus during math tests, characterized by racing thoughts and moments of mental blankness (M=3.68), item 4 about having a lack of confidence in my abilities during math tests, regardless of the thoroughness of my preparation (M=3.73), all rated as high.	Table 3.2 on the category – personal struggles with problem-solving under the theme – Challenges with Mathematics Concepts and Skills	Merging – converging	Students display high anxiety and struggle with assessments, indicating a lack of confidence and difficulty With math concepts, which hampers their academic performance.
Social Factor	Table 3 on the indicator of social factors specifically item 1 about perceiving others to have a more mathematical or logical mind than I do (M=3.61), item 3 about finding myself worrying about other people’s math abilities and comparing them to my own (M=3.53), both rated as high.	Table 3.2 core ideas- on the category - lack of motivation under the theme - Lack of motivation and.	Merging – Converging	Students perceive themselves as less capable compared to peers, leading to social anxiety and decreased motivation, which contributes to overall math anxiety and disinterest.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

First, the perceived level of mathematics anxiety among first-year college students is notably high. This elevated anxiety manifests across physical and emotional, assessment, and social factors, indicating a pervasive issue affecting various aspects of students' mathematical experiences. The consistency of these observations suggests that mathematics anxiety is a significant and persistent challenge for first-year students. This high level of anxiety likely impacts students' ability to engage with mathematical concepts effectively, potentially hindering their academic performance and overall relationship with the subject. Recognizing the prevalence and intensity of this anxiety is crucial for developing targeted interventions and support systems.

Second, the experiences of first-year college students in learning mathematics are diverse and multifaceted, as revealed through in-depth interviews. The thematic analysis uncovered four primary themes: Encountering Cognitive Challenges, Experiencing Emotional and Psychological Crises, Lack of Motivation and Interest, and Challenges with Mathematics Concepts and Skills. These themes highlight the complex interplay of cognitive, emotional, and motivational factors that contribute to mathematics anxiety. Students reported struggling with abstract concepts, feeling overwhelmed by the pressure of assessments, and experiencing a diminished sense of confidence in their mathematical abilities. The emergence of these themes underscores the need for comprehensive support strategies that address not only academic challenges but also the psychological and emotional aspects of learning mathematics.

Lastly, the quantitative data significantly corroborates with the qualitative findings, providing a robust and comprehensive understanding of mathematics anxiety among first-year students. The integration of both data sets reveals a strong convergence, with the qualitative themes aligning closely with the quantitative measurements of anxiety levels. This correlation strengthens the validity of the study's findings and offers a more nuanced perspective on the nature and impact of mathematics anxiety. Both quantitative and qualitative results confirm that anxiety in learning mathematics has both positive and negative effects, with the negative impacts being more pronounced and far-reaching. This convergence of data emphasizes the critical need for targeted interventions and supportive educational strategies to mitigate the adverse effects of mathematics anxiety and enhance students' mathematical experiences and performance.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were being drawn:

Since the status of mathematics anxiety reveals that among the three indicators of mathematics anxiety, the assessment factor has the highest mean, which affects how students learn their lessons the most, it is recommended that schools implement comprehensive test preparation and support strategies. By providing regular study skills workshops, practice tests, and access to tutoring services, students will be better prepared for mathematics assessments, reducing their anxiety. They may also benefit from formative assessments that offer constructive feedback, helping them identify areas for improvement without the pressure of high-stakes testing. Furthermore, schools should foster an environment where students can openly discuss their anxieties and seek help, promoting a culture of support and understanding.

Moreover, based on the qualitative phase results on the lived experiences of first-year students with regards to their anxiety in learning mathematics, students may develop new methods to manage their anxiety. They may benefit from enhancing their understanding of mathematics through additional resources such as online tutorials and interactive learning tools, which allow them to grasp difficult concepts at their own pace. Additionally, staying updated with the latest educational resources and technologies can provide students with innovative ways to approach their studies, ensuring they are not left behind. Hence, from their experiences, students may learn to utilize these strategies to maximize their learning potential and reduce their anxiety effectively.

Furthermore, those differentiated experiences shared by first-year students with regards to their anxiety in mathematics can be used to meet their learning needs. Schools can facilitate the sharing of these strategies among students, creating a supportive community where students can learn from each other's experiences. Also, new approaches may be developed as educational technologies and methodologies advance, providing students with additional tools to manage their anxiety. As educational practices evolve, these strategies will continue to be refined and improved, offering students better ways to cope with their anxiety.

In addition, the researcher recommends the intensification of support for mathematics anxiety management through training and seminars addressed to first-year students and faculty alike. There may be conduct of webinars and seminars pertinent to anxiety management. The institution may also send students and faculty delegates to different off-campus and online trainings and seminars related to managing mathematics anxiety. This approach ensures that both students and faculty are equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to address anxiety effectively.

Lastly, it is also recommended for students to engage in self-reflection and seek help when needed. They must be cautious of the potential negative effects that unchecked anxiety can bring. Enhancing their self-awareness and knowledge about anxiety management techniques can help students use these strategies effectively, maximizing their learning potential and overall academic success. These measures aim to create a supportive and effective learning environment, helping students overcome their mathematics anxiety and achieve academic success.

References

Akkaya, S., & Platt, K. (2022). An Investigation of the Relationship between the Parents' Math Literacy Self-Efficacy and Their Math Anxieties. *Educational Policy Analysis and Strategic Research*, V17. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1352295.pdf>

- Anugrah, T. M., Kusmayadi, T. A., & Fitriana, L. (2019). Mathematics anxiety in dealing math exams. *Journal of Physics. Conference Series*, 1157, 032101. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1157/3/032101>
- Azizah, L. N., Mahmudi, A., & Retnawati, H. (2019). Profile of students' mathematics anxiety. *Journal of Physics. Conference Series*, 1320(1), 012105. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1320/1/012105>
- Balt, M., Börnert-Ringleb, M., & Orbach, L. (2022). Reducing math anxiety in school children: A systematic review of intervention research. *Frontiers in Education*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2022.798516>
- Bangalan, R. C., & Hipona, J. B. (2020). Mathematics in the modern world as a science of patterns with an integration of outcome based teaching-learning approaches. *Cosmos Journal of Engineering & Technology A Refereed Research Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.46360/cosmos.et.xxxxxxx>
- Barroso, C., Ganley, C., McGraw, A., Geer, E., Hart, S., & Daucourt, M. (2020). A meta-analysis of the relation between math anxiety and math achievement. *Psychological Bulletin*, 147(2), 134–168. <https://doi.org/10.1037/bul0000307>
- Brewster, B. J. M., & Miller, T. (2020). Missed opportunity in mathematics anxiety. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 15(3), em0600. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iejme/8405>
- Brezavscek, A., Jerebic, J., ORCID, Rus, G., ORCID, & Žnidarsic, A. (2020). Factors Influencing Mathematics Achievement of University Students of Social Sciences. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math8122134>
- BU Journal of Graduate Studies in Education*, Volume 14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math8122134>
- Bringula, R., Reguyal, J. J., Tan, D. D., & Ulfa, S. (2021). Mathematics self-concept and challenges of learners in an online learning environment during COVID-19 pandemic. *Smart Learning Environments*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-021-00168-5>
- Buratta, L., Piccalillis, M., Lanfaloni, G., Ilicini, S., Bedetti, C., & Elisei, S. (2019). Mathematics anxiety and cognitive performance in adolescent students. *Psychiatriadanubina*. https://www.psichiatriadanubina.com/UserDocsImages/pdf/dnb_vol31_noSuppl%203/dnb_vol31_noSuppl%203_479.pdf
- Cenberci, S. (2023). The Points to be Considered while Developing the Activities for the Mathematics Course. *International e-Journal of Educational Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.31458/iejes.1297016>
- Cevikbas, M., Kaiser, G., & Schukajlow, S. (2024). Trends in mathematics education and insights from a meta-review and bibliometric analysis of review studies. *ZDM Mathematics Education*, 56, 165–188. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-024-01587-7>
- Chew, S. L., & Cerbin, W. J. (2021). The cognitive challenges of effective teaching. *The Journal of Economic Education*, 52(1), 17–40. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220485.2020.1845266>
- De Jong, T. (2010). Cognitive load theory, educational research, and instructional design: Some food for thought. *Instructional Science*, 38(2), 105–134. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11251-009-9110-0>
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2012). Self-Determination Theory. In E. Higgins (Ed.), *Handbook of Theories of Social Psychology: Volume 1* (Vol. 1, pp. 416–437). SAGE Publications Ltd.
- Deveci, O., & Karademir, C. (2019). Investigation of the 5th Grade Students' Engagements in Mathematics Courses towards Student Opinions. *European Journal of Educational Research*. <https://doi.org/10.12973/eu-jer.8.1.337>
- Dicheva, D., Guy, B., Yorgov, V., Dichev, C., Irwin, K., Mickle, C., (2021). A Study of Using Virtual Currency in a Discrete Mathematics Course. *IEEE (Global Engineering Education Conference)*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EDUCON46332.2021.9453893>
- Dodongan, E., & Casocot, N. (2022). Math anxiety, learning engagement and perceived usefulness of technology as predictors to mathematics performance of students. *United International Journal for Research & Technology*. <https://uijrt.com/articles/v3/i4/UIJRTV3I40012.pdf>
- Doleshal, B. (2022). Escape the Semester: Game-Based Pedagogy in a Math Course for Non-Science Majors. *PRIMUS - Problems, Resources, and Issues in Mathematics Undergraduate Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10511970.2022.2122091>
- Eysenck, M. W., Derakshan, N., Santos, R., & Calvo, M. G. (2007). Anxiety and cognitive performance: Attentional control theory. *Emotion (Washington, D.C.)*, 7(2), 336–353. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1528-3542.7.2.336>
- Furner, J. M., & Duffy, M. L. (2022). Addressing math anxiety in a STEM world: Preventative, supportive, and corrective strategies for the inclusive classroom. *European Journal of STEM Education*, 7(1), 11. <https://doi.org/10.20897/ejsteme/12645>
- Guzman, B., Rodríguez, C., & Ferreira, R. (2021). Longitudinal Performance in Basic Numerical Skills Mediates the Relationship Between Socio-Economic Status and Mathematics Anxiety: Evidence From Chile. *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.611395>

- Kelly, S., Croucher, S. M., Kim, K. Y., Permyakova, T., Turdubaeva, E., Rocker, K. T., Eskiçorapçi, N., Stanaliev, G., Orunbekov, B., & Rimkeeratikul, S. (2022). A general math anxiety measure. *Education Sciences*, 12(6), 370. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci12060370>
- Kihwele, J. E., & Mkomwa, J. (2023). Promoting students' interest and achievement in mathematics through "King and Queen of Mathematics" initiative. *Journal of Research in Innovative Teaching & Learning*, 16(1), 115–133. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jrit-12-2021-0083>
- Kihwele, J. E., & Mkomwa, J. (2023). Promoting students' interest and achievement in mathematics through "King and Queen of Mathematics" initiative. *Journal of Research in Innovative Teaching & Learning*, 16(1), 115–133. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jrit-12-2021-0083>
- Klados, M., Paraskevopoulos, E., Pandria, N., & Bamidis, P. (2019). The Impact of Math Anxiety on Working Memory: A Cortical Activations and Cortical Functional Connectivity EEG Study, in *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 15027-15039. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2892808>.
- Lau, N. T. T., Hawes, Z., Tremblay, P., & Ansari, D. (2022). Disentangling the individual and contextual effects of math anxiety: A global perspective. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 119(7). <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2115855119>
- Lazarus, R. S., & Folkman, S. (1984). *Stress, appraisal, and coping*. New York: Springer Publishing Company. <https://www.springerpub.com/stress-and-emotion-9780826102614>
- Leikin, R. (Ed.). (2023). *Mathematical Challenges For All*. Springer International Publishing. <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-031-18868-8>
- Li, Q., Cho, H., Cosso, J., et al. (2021). Relations Between Students' Mathematics Anxiety and Motivation to Learn Mathematics: A Meta-Analysis. *Educ Psychol Rev*, 33, 1017–1049. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-020-09589-z>
- Luttenberger, S., Wimmer, S., & Paechter, M. (2018). Spotlight on math anxiety. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, 11, 311–322. <https://doi.org/10.2147/prbm.s141421>
- Michaelides, M. P., Brown, G. T. L., Eklöf, H., & Papanastasiou, E. C. (2019). The relationship of motivation with achievement in mathematics. In *IEA Research for Education* (pp. 9–23). Springer International Publishing. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-26183-2_2
- Moscoso, P., Anobile, G., Primi, C., & Arrighi, R. (2020). Math Anxiety Mediates the Link Between Number Sense and Math Achievements in High Math Anxiety Young Adults. *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.01095>
- Moscoso, P., Castaldi, E., Arrighi, R., Primi, C., Caponi, C., Buonincontro, S., Bolognin, F., & Anobil, G. (2022). Mathematics and Numerosity but Not Visuo-Spatial Working Memory Correlate with Mathematical Anxiety in Adults. *Brain Science*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci12040422>
- Namkung, J. M. (2019). The Relation Between Mathematics Anxiety and Mathe Performance Among School-Aged Students: A Meta-Analysis. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654319843494>
- Obersteiner, A., Dresler, T., Bieck, S. M., & Moeller, K. (2019). Understanding Fractions: Integrating Results from Mathematics Education, Cognitive Psychology, and Neuroscience. In: Norton, A., & Alibali, M. W. (eds) *Constructing Number*. Research in Mathematics Education. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-00491-0_7
- Ongcoy, P. J. B., Jasmin, D. R. A., Guimalal, I. P., Guinita, S. S., & Iligan, A. M. M. (2023). Experiences and mathematics anxiety of STEM students. *Journal of Mathematics and Science Teacher*, 3(1), em028. <https://doi.org/10.29333/mathsciteacher/12870>
- Onoshakpokaiye, O. (2023). An Overview Of Reasoning Ability In Mathematics And Mathematics Achievement Of Students In Tertiary Institution. *International Journal of Indonesian Education and Teaching*. <https://e-journal.usd.ac.id/index.php/IJIET/article/view/5988>
- Piccirilli, M., Lanfalconi, G., Buratta, L., Ciotti, B., Lepri, A., Azzarelli, C., Ilicini, S., D'Alessandro, P., & Sandro Elisei. (2023). Assessment of math anxiety as a potential tool to identify students at risk of poor acquisition of new math skills: A longitudinal study of grade 9 Italian students. *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1185677>
- Rada, E., & Lucietto, A. (2022). Math Anxiety – A literature review on confounding factors. *Journal of research in science, mathematics and technology education*. <https://org.doi:10.31756/jrsmte.12040>
- Rada, E., & Lucietto, A. M. (2022). Math anxiety – A literature review on confounding factors. *Journal of Research in Science Mathematics and Technology Education*, 5(2), 117–129. <https://doi.org/10.31756/jrsmte.12040>

- Reynvoet, B., Ribner, A., Elliott, L., Steenkiste, M., Sasanguie, D., & Libertus, M. (2021). Making sense of the relation between number sense and math. *Journal of Numerical Cognition*. <https://doi.org/10.5964/jnc.6059>
- Rozgonjuk, D., Kraav, T., Mikkor, K., et al. (2020). Mathematics anxiety among STEM and social sciences students: The roles of mathematics self-efficacy, and deep and surface approach to learning. *IJ STEM Ed*, 7, 46. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-020-00246>
- Ruff, S., & Boes, S. (2023). The Sum of All Fears: The Effects of Math Anxiety on Math Achievement in Fifth Grade Students and the Implications for School Counselors. The University of West Georgia. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1084441.pdf>
- Schukajlow, S., Rakoczy, K., & Pekrun, R. (2023). Emotions and motivation in mathematics education: Where we are today and where we need to go. *ZDM: The International Journal on Mathematics Education*, 55(2), 249–267. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-022-01463-2>
- Schukajlow, S., Rakoczy, K., & Pekrun, R. (2023). Emotions and motivation in mathematics education: Where we are today and where we need to go. *ZDM: The International Journal on Mathematics Education*, 55(2), 249–267. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-022-01463-2>
- Shamim, N., & Kang, M. (2021). Impact of Math's Anxiety on Student's Attitude towards Quantitative Research. *Journal of Education and Humanities Research*. <http://web.uob.edu.pk/uob/Journals/jehr/jehr.php>
- Simonton, K. L., & Garn, A. C. (2020). Control–value theory of achievement emotions: A closer look at student value appraisals and enjoyment. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 81(101910), 101910. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2020.101910>
- Singh, S. (2022). Mathematics Anxiety: A Mixed Methods Approach to Understanding Secondary Students' Avoidance of Mathematics Impacting Secondary Mathematics Enrollment. University of Tennessee. https://trace.tennessee.edu/utk_graddiss/7319
- Skovsmose, O. (2021). Mathematics and crises. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 108(1–2), 369–383. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10649-021-10037-0>
- Szucs, D., McLellan, R., & Dowker, A. (2019). Understanding mathematics anxiety. Nuffield Foundation. <https://www.nuffieldfoundation.org/project/understanding-mathematics-anxiety>
- Tan, J., Mao, J., Jiang, Y., & Gao, M. (2021). The influence of academic emotions on learning effects: A systematic review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(18), 9678. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18189678>
- Velez, A. J. B., Dayaganon, D. G., Robigid, J., Demorito, J., Villegas, J., & Gomez, D. (2023, April 14). Difficulties and Coping Strategies in Understanding Mathematical Concepts in a Private Higher Education in Tagum City, Davao del Norte, Philippines. Researchgate.net. <https://doi.org/10.59120/drj.v14i1.10>
- Wang, S., Perry, L., Malpique, A., & Ide, T. (2023). Factors predicting mathematics achievement in PISA: A systematic review. An IEA-ETS Research Institute Journal. <https://largescaleassessmentsineducation.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s40536-023-00174-4>
- Wang, C., Xu, Q., & Fei, W.-Q. (2024). The effect of student-perceived teacher support on math anxiety: Chain mediation of teacher-student relationship and math self-efficacy. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1333012>
- Wang, X. S., Perry, L. B., & Malpique, A. (2023). Factors predicting mathematics achievement in PISA: A systematic review. *Large-scale Assess Educ*, 11, 24. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40536-023-00174-8>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Alvin D. Libre

Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Jubert E. Gulo, MAEd

Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology – Philippines